

ESGF Node Survey: Projects, storage and future plans

CMIP-International Project Office April 2025

Responding nodes

- A survey was conducted of 53 nodes by CMIP-IPO commencing on March 11 2025 via Airtable. The survey covered topics such as node type, hardware, active and archived projects, and data storage.
- 26 nodes responded to the survey by the deadline of 03 April 2025.
- 6 nodes responded to the survey after 03 April (contact details / technical issue).
- 21 nodes did not respond to the survey as of 11 April 2025 (~ 40%).

Node Status - Is the node currently active Yes, or No?

- YES = 28
- NO = 5*
- Cross-referencing survey data with ESGF Node Status landing page found:
 - 5 nodes **online** and **did not respond** to survey – 3 found to be redundant
 - 10 nodes **not online** and **did respond** to survey – 7 found to be redundant
 - 8 nodes **not online** and **did not respond** to survey – all 8 found to be redundant.
- CMIP-IPO contacted any un-responsive nodes, 7 replied with new contact details and in several cases the node status was active – contrary to the information on ESGF.
- ESGF Node Status page found to be generating ‘false positive’.

* Three nodes are not active due to technical problems and aim to be back online in 2025

Node Infrastructure - what type of node is currently operating?

Node Infrastructure - what hardware type?

Projects – active and archived

Archived projects – which projects are associated with the node?

Number of nodes hosting:

- CMIP5 = 16
- Other = 15 (included CORDEX-FPCONV, SPECS etc.)
- CORDEX-CMIP5 = 10
- CMIP3 = 6
- CMIP4 = 1

Nodes with 'Plans for storage and retrieval of historical ESGF data' :

- Tape drive = 4
- Hard-disk = 23
- Other = 5
- *Mix between tape and disk*
- *Private cloud with OpenStack*
- *Serve rarely used data from tape*

Active projects - which projects are associated with the node?

Number of nodes hosting:

- CMIP6 = 28
- Other = 11
- CMIP7 = 11*
- CORDEX-CMIP6 = 9
- CORDEX-CMIP7 = 5*
- input4MIPs = 5
- obs4MIPs = 4
- CMIP6Plus = 4

- Other projects:
- Hi-Res
- CORDEX-Adjust,
- PMIP3, CMIP6-Adjust
- MPI-Driven-LE
- PalMod2, MPI-GE
- COSMO-REA
- CORDEX-Reklies
- CORDEX-FPSCONV
- PRIMAVERA

* Nodes intending to host these data once available

Future projects - Plans for 2025 and beyond

Storage

CMIP projects - total storage (PB)

Nodes hosting:

- CMIP5
- CMIP6

- Two nodes support obs4MIPs and input4MIPs, both hosting 10 TB of data.
- 11 nodes host over 1 PB of CMIP5 and CMIP6 data.
- One node hosts CMIP4 data.
- Three nodes host CMIP3 data totaling 147 TB.

CORDEX projects - Storage (PB)

* UK total CORDEX = 0.04 PB

All projects - Storage (PB)

- All CMIP, CORDEX, Input4MIPs, Obs4MIPs data.
- Assumes all nodes in each reporting country are active.
- **CMIP 7 AFT ~ 6 to 10 Pb**

Funding

Funding - How is the node currently funded?

Number of nodes

Institutional funding = 20

Project-based funding = 17

National funding agency = 15

Other = 2 *

• 14 nodes have a mix of funding types for ESGF activities

*

*In-kind funding from national meteorological office
We provide the service and the storage with an agreement*

Funding – How will this change over the duration of CMIP7?

Number of nodes

No change = 22

Increased = 8

Decreased = 3

- In answer to the prompt 'Require assistance in seeking funding'
- 19 nodes replied 'Yes'.
 - 11 have 'no change'
 - 4 have 'increased funding'
 - 3 have 'decreased funding'

CDNOT Feedback

Help with migration

- In response to the question *'If Tier 2, would more information about migration options be useful?'* the reply was:
 - **YES = 19**
 - **NO = 4**
 - **No response = 10**
- In response to the question *'If Tier 1, are there plans to migrate from solr to another platform?'* there were six replies:
 - *Yes, underway now*
 - *We plan to migrate the local data but not decided on the technology yet*
 - *esm.ac.cn*
 - *ESGF-NG (shared with US/UK STAC)*
 - *Planning to switch to Elastic Search when the rest of ESGF transitions*
 - *Globus Search*
 - *Elastic Search*

What information from CDNOT would be valuable to Node managers?

- *Centralized DevOps Support to maintain deployment packages, updates, and CI/CD pipelines. Simplified Deployment with pre-packaged solutions to deploy ESGF nodes. Modular, Scalable Nodes allowing small sites to deploy lightweight nodes that can scale up as needed. Develop a strategy to support multiple access protocols can coexist on small, medium, and Tier 1 nodes. Dataset Visibility to ensure datasets from small and medium nodes are registered automatically in ESGF catalogues.*
- *Recipes for ESGF stack deployment*
- *Updated documentation on (data) node management and publisher suite.*
- *Clear and simple documentation on basic Data node requirements and setup, including hardware (system memory) and infrastructure (network bandwidth). Minimum expected requirements for data nodes as this is important information when requesting hardware/infrastructure changes. It is difficult to request specific specifications without knowledge of how the entire Federated network is expected to perform.*
- *We have received plenty of ad-hoc help and hope to continue receiving it.*
- *We need better documentation and there must be consequences for data nodes not following the node requirements.*
- *CMIP-IPO support for CMIP6, CMIP7 data.*
- *We plan to upgrade node to the new Kubernetes based software stack, so it could be useful to have support on how to transfer data from the old and on how to publish new data with the new node.*
- *Information coordination.*
- *CDNOT support*

What information from CDNOT would be valuable to Node managers?

- *We feel well-informed via the existing mailing lists.*
- *Comprehensive software manuals and diversified technical support channels.*
- *Timely and frequent communication regarding the status of development for the ESGF architecture.*
- *Clear yet detailed installation/upgrade procedures for newly released software, along with a platform to communicate questions regarding such upgrades (i.e. usage of the ESGF slack channel, etc).*
- *Prompt communication with regards to updates surrounding the CMIP data request and additional instructions for node managers, if needed.*
- *Supplementary information about data publication, retraction, and errata.*
- *Information on the installation, maintenance, and updating of node software. Future plans and prospects for ESGF and CMIP.*
- *It would be helpful to have more detailed documentation on node installation and operation.*
- *Advice regarding CMIP5/CMIP6/CORDEX-CMIP5 'republication' strategies. Support for new publication process for AR7 FT/CMIP7/CORDEX-CMIP6.*
- *Continue to host meetings where node operators can participate in and be made aware of changes with policy, federation, etc.*
- *Guidance on recommended software versions and deployment approach(es). Help transitioning CMIP6 data products to new infrastructure. Roadmap of future releases and plans.*
- *Be an advocate for well-informed data files. Support for data providers to generate files that meet QC criteria.*

Survey Feedback

In response to: “If you have any other feedback regarding this questionnaire or ESGF Node infrastructure and operation, please comment below”

- *Note: in the question field about "Which modelling centres use your node infrastructure?" there are missing CORDEX institution, i.e. UCAN*
- *We are tentatively expecting to publish CORDEX-CMIP6 data to our current data node but have not as of yet. We have acquired the hardware for a new data node to serve CMIP7 data specifically. This server will act as another single data node serving only CMIP7 data (CMIP6/5 will continue to be served on the existing node). We have been unable to acquire funding for a GLOBUS license to support our data node, and this will likely remain the case unless GLOBUS becomes an explicit requirement of the ESGF project. We will only support HTTPS downloads for the foreseeable future, but if we look into funding for GLOBUS again some assistance would be appreciated.*
- *RCM modelling centres don't seem to be options in the list. We store CORDEX-CMIP5 RCM output from DMI, Hungarian Met Office, KNMI, OURANOS, Univ. Quebec a Montreal, Univ. Gent and Univ. Liege.*
- *We are deploying another data node for the OptimESM project data with the new Kubernetes based software stack. So, it could be useful to have support on registering that new data node within the ESGF federation. It could be useful also to have support on publishing data.*
- *We provide services by dividing them among multiple nodes for each CMIP and model. Our current ESGF nodes are active, but we have not been able to publish any data for last one year because we cannot follow the update of ESGF node software, mainly due to the lack of experienced person. We would gratefully appreciate any help from ESGF to update our current version and install new version planned to be available this year.*
- *The evolution of the CNRM-CERFACS node is somehow unusual in that it will continue to host the CMIP/CORDEX production of the CNRM-CERFACS centre but will no longer be an ESGF node. Our server replacing esg1.umr-cnrm will have its disks ‘exported’ and directly accessible from the IPSL node. But people from the CNRM-CERFACS centre will continue to be in charge of publishing on ESGF with ‘publisher’ rights on the IPSL node. We will therefore be interested in any information relating to future ESGF publication procedures.*
- *Our server is currently closed due to technical issues but will be operated for CMIP7.*

Thank You

[@wcrp-cmip.org](https://twitter.com/wcrp-cmip)

[wcrp-cmip](https://www.linkedin.com/company/wcrp-cmip)

cmip-ipo@esa.int